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**Title: The Cultural factors that Influence Customer Online Buying
Decision Between Morocco and United Kingdom**

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Abstract

The study used a confirmatory factor analysis based on the UTAUT model to investigate the factors that have contributed to the growth of e-commerce in both Morocco and the United Kingdom. The strength of the relationships between the several factors is then analyzed using Hofstede's theory. A total of one hundred persons participated in this study by filling out questionnaires. They were drawn from Morocco and United Kingdom. The survey questions were not developed to gather insights into the consumption of specific goods or services. However, they were designed solely to expose the common internet buying habits of people in both countries. Using the UTAUT model, this comprehensive study shows the study's findings and establishes its validity in both nations. Additionally, the study offers some practical recommendations for encouraging online shopping. It also shows that UTAUT scales are valid and reliable, and it recommended more research be done to enhance the model.

1. Introduction

E-commerce is a new paradigm in the business world, one in which information and communication technology are the only driver of growth, allowing businesses to reach more people for less money and with more competitive advantages. However, in this environment, consumer behavior and how they make decisions are different than what marketers are used to seeing in traditional business. What the internet provides goes well beyond just mediating business transactions. The opportunities for stores to advertise themselves online via social media, email, and websites continue to expand as the world becomes more and more reliant on digital technologies (Civeleket al. 2020). Retailers are increasing their market share with the help of e-commerce because it enables them to find the best suppliers and the greatest compatible business associates, both domestically and internationally, and to distribute to customers more rapidly, inexpensively, and conveniently. The worldwide computer network has recently come into the spotlight for several reasons, including the reduction of administrative costs, reduced prices, and fewer overhead expenditures. Internet shopping has made it possible for people to purchase virtually anything, whenever they want, wherever they are, and with no additional fees. Moreover, customers can expect prompt shipping and a customer-friendly return policy (Alraja and Kashoob 2019). What customers want—what drives demand for goods and services—is intrinsically linked to the decision-making process. Shoppers can satisfy their needs in a straightforward manner. Because most consumers do not recognize their own requirements or understand how to articulate them, defining them is a challenging process. Also, keep in mind that each one of your customers has unique needs (Limet al. 2016). As a complex and ever-changing process, it can be difficult to grasp what motivates customers to make a purchase. Customers must deal with a variety of issues, and their activities are deeply affected by a wide range of contextual variables. Since the dawn of commerce, when individuals assumed the position of consumers with access to a selection of products and services, this process has persisted in modern society (Stofkova, K.R., Laitkep, D. and Stofkova, Z., 2022).

1.1 Purpose of the research

The major purpose of this research is to comprehend the factors that have led to the explosive expansion of online shopping in the UK. We were surprised to learn, upon moving to UK, how at ease people are with making internet purchases. Meanwhile, online businesses in Morocco are still having difficulties attracting customers to purchase their products. At first, we assumed that higher levels of income and education would be the primary factors encouraging Internet use among in Britain. The longer we stayed, the more we realized that there are a variety of cultural elements that influence British citizens' preferences while making online purchases. We've

learned from talking to my British colleagues that the British have a higher rate of trust in internet retailers than the Moroccans do. Rather than continue to assume, we decided to do a research study to investigate Explain the emergence of online purchasing in the United Kingdom in light of the cultural contrasts between the two countries.

1.2 Dilemma of investigation

Online buyers' habits are vastly different from those of traditional customers. Liao et al. (2000) claim that businesses are creating online stores to take advantage of new telecommunications technologies and thereby increase the value of their business. Due to these two main reasons, they are urged to do so. It is now much simpler than ever before to set up and maintain an online store for your products. It is also convenient to buy and sell goods online. However, making this business profitable is difficult and complex. There are many factors to consider, including an extensive knowledge of the culture's internet buying habits. This study primary objective is to examine the impact of cultural differences, such as those between Morocco and United Kingdom, on internet buying behavior. In this way, the major study issue is broken down to the following questions:

- Factors affecting online purchases in United Kingdom and Morocco?
- How does individualism vs. collectivism affect online shopping?
- Does Culture affect the online buying behavior between Morocco and United Kingdom?

1.3 The depth of the research

This investigation included more than just locals in United Kingdom and Morocco. Although this research was conducted only in UK and Morocco, it made no distinctions based on the nationality of the participants. People from both UK and Morocco were grouped together as one big group. Consequently, all survey forms had to be written in English to guarantee that the entire population being surveyed would have the same understanding. Furthermore, no questions have been asked of the respondents that are meant to provide information about their nationality, they were only asked about if they made any purchase 6 months at least either in Morocco or UK. No specific goods or services were targeted in this analysis. Since only online customers are of interest, a survey targeted to their shopping habits

was devised. As a result, to assess the respondents' conduct, only broad questions have been posed. The questions were not meant to reveal patterns in the online sales of products in either the Moroccan or British markets. Instead, they focused on pinpointing the motives for making an online purchase.

1.4 Planning of research

These five themes make up the rest of this thesis. The second and third themes build upon this initial subject by reviewing the literature on online buying behavior and trust presenting important theories that form the basis of the present investigation. Theme 4 explains how this quantitative investigation was carried out. Data analysis is presented in the fifth theme. Data analysis in the context of the underlying theory is the subject of the sixth theme covered. Finally, we discuss the study's limits and potential applications in the last theme.

2. Literature review

2.1 Online buying behavior

A person's purchasing habits are the product of a wide variety of factors, both macro and microsocial, where each can be identified independently. Individuals' shopping-related decisions are directly tied to the allocation of scarce resources like time, money, and energy. Questions about what customers buy, where they buy it, why they buy it, how often they buy it, how often they use it, how they rate it after buying it, and how those ratings affect future sales are all part of this broader category. The use of innovations is now crucial to the success of merchants. They must capitalize on everything the Internet age has to offer, particularly the improved targeting capabilities that come with it (Širola, D., 2022). Since e-commerce is opening so many doors for shoppers, businesses in the sector are scrambling to figure out how to draw in the largest possible clientele. When it comes to driving traffic to their online store, retailers need to do two things: make their websites easy to use and keep their social media marketing campaigns actively managed (Lim et al. 2016). Online shopping has opened a world of possibilities for both buyers and sellers (Stofkova, K.R., Laitkep, D. and Stofkova, Z., 2022). There are numerous benefits to shopping online rather than in a physical store. Customers can make reservations or make purchases at any time, from any location. Cost savings are only one of the numerous reasons why many businesses do not operate their own retail outlets. Some businesses are entirely online, while others may

share office space with another firm or operate entirely online. Most of the major retailers have been building up showrooms recently, allowing customers to physically interact with products before purchasing them online (Lim et al. 2016). Findings from a survey conducted in Slovakia suggest that cellphones are rapidly replacing desktop computers as the preferred method of accessing the internet. Companies are being pushed to innovate and modify client touchpoints as smartphone shopping becomes more commonplace (Kakalejicik and Bucko, 2018). One study found that smartphones were the second most popular digital device used by women for internet shopping, after laptops (Stefko et al. 2019). Consumers have flocked online over the past decade, and this trend shows no signs of slowing down. This expanding market is particularly interested in exploring novel online distribution methods, such as social media and e-mail newsletters (Civelek et al. 2020). Companies are forced to think outside the box in response to new technologies. The use of influencers in marketing is a new pressing requirement brought on by the convergence of mobile devices and social media platforms. Some social media do influence customer behavior, according to a 2021 study that draws nebulous inferences from statistical data of consumer purchase behavior in social media. That's the conclusion we've come to as well (Ali Taha et al. 2021).

2.3 Trust

Trust can be defined as a set of beliefs that an individual holds based on his or her impressions of characteristics (Flavián et al., 2006). Internet retailing adoption is influenced by trust; hence e-tailers should develop websites that communicate trust (Gefen et al., 2003). Several variables affect users' trust in websites, including website usability, security and privacy guarantees, and the quality of product information (Chen and Dibb 2010). Researchers from Finland and Sweden discovered that a person's confidence in e-commerce is related to their long-term orientation and collectivism. Previous research indicates that trust is greater in collectivist cultures than in individualist cultures (Kelley, 2003). It has a positive effect on the disposition of trust, meaning that commercial partnerships in long-term oriented cultures are frequently established over the long term (Hallikainen Laukkanen, 2018)

2.4 Perceived risk

Business managers should consider perceived risk as significant as other criteria, such as

pricing, in a research study on Alibaba.com. Risk and purchase intent are closely linked; if the risk tied to the product is high, the purchase of intent will be low and vice versa (Sharma, V.M. and Klein, A., 2020). Alternatively, detailed numerous distinct categories of perceived risk from the consumer's perspective. Financial, product, security, timeliness, social, and psychological hazards are some of the most cited. According to this study, social risk was determined to be the most significant risk related with the desire to buy online. As a result of the criticism of family and friends, and the anxiety, of purchasing an item online, there is social risk. (Ariffin et al. 2018) Consumers are vulnerable to three types of risk: those associated with the goods itself, those associated with the transaction itself, and those associated with their own minds. The danger of a subpar experience with a product bought online is known as "product risk." This occurs when a buyer makes a purchase without first physically inspecting the item. The risk associated with making a payment to an unknown recipient, known as "transaction risk," might have serious consequences. The anxiousness and unease that a buyer experiences from placing an order to receiving their shipment is known as psychological risk. Decision-making difficulty will increase under such circumstances. The product will be subjected to in-depth customer evaluations and brand comparisons. Perceived risk, uncertainty, and repercussions are the three factors that have been identified as influencing consumers' decisions to make purchases online. (Bangun, C.S. and Handra, T., 2021)

2. Decision making process

Money is exchanged while purchasing and selling conventional products and services. The salesperson informs the consumer, displays the goods for the client, and includes instructions for use on the product's packaging; the customer then decides whether to make a purchase. Consumers' purchasing habits have shifted as the Internet has become more widely available, thus businesses who can keep up with the times and adapt to the changing preferences of their target market will be more successful. As a result, marketplaces where goods and services can be bought and sold online have emerged. They appear during a time when online commerce has supplanted the need for human salespeople. It is common practice to investigate system design to better inform buyers' choices. In 2017, Pham, for instance, did research on the effects of an overview of the online procedure on customer satisfaction. Additionally, the success or influence of customers' purchase decisions is highly dependent

on the design of all procedures at each stage (Pham and Ahammad, 2017). In subsequent research, Ozkara has looked at how a customer's satisfaction with their online shopping experience is influenced by their perception of the information they receive (Ozkara et al., 2017).

2.1 Online purchase decision-making process

Online buying Before making a final purchase choice, the user of online trading goods or services must complete the DMP procedure. The primary focus of the study will be on the utility of DMP for developing platforms or online tools that comply with the convenience of buying decisions. Consequently, making purchases will be easier and more informed. DMP is crucial because customers who purchase products or services online must complete this step prior to the actual transaction. Huang and Benyoucef concluded their study on consumer purchasing behavior in 2017. The design to comprehend a customer's selection has proven difficult. They have examined five ways in which online DMP can influence consumers' shopping decisions (Huang and Benyoucef, 2017). In 2018, Karimi presented a study on differences in customer behavior, consumer traits, and purchasing decisions. Product information has influenced customers' purchasing decisions while making purchases (Karimi et al., 2018). People employ their reasoning ability to make decisions (Faulds et al., 2018). In a 1959 book, Simon outlined the three stages of stepwise decision-making as intelligence (gathering information), design (exploring alternatives), and choosing (making a decision). In 2002, Liang and Lai outlined in detail the following five phases of the purchasing decision process:

Figure 1 Consumer Decision Making Process

- **Need recognition:** To come to terms with one's own wants and needs in terms of purchases is an action.

- **Searching for information** is a process that involves, among other things, searching for that information. As a result, there may be many people who are marketable to employers.
- **Evaluation of alternatives** is to assess and equate candidates that can be purchased, which is step three of evaluation.
- **Purchasing:** is the act of exchanging money for goods or services.
- **Post-Purchasing:** Five Actions taken after a purchase has been made, including as evaluation, suggestion, complaint, and refund

3. Model of intention, adoption, and continuance (MIAC)

The paradigm for understanding shoppers' actions on the web relies on three main ideas. academics specializing in consumer behavior mainly looked at what aspects impact online shoppers' adoption and use of online shops. Due to the rise of e-commerce, these professionals have learned that their rivals are always just a mouseclick away. Therefore, businesses shouldn't build their marketing tactics to persuade customers to buy their goods exclusively on the insights provided by applicable theories of online customer behavior. They should teach them, whenever possible, how to keep these individuals as clients. Recent interest has also increased in the investigation of the concept of consumer repurchase. Intention, adoption, and tenacity are the three pillar concepts of the online customer behavior paradigm. (Cheung et al. 2003).

The MIAC model emerged as the first consumer behavior framework to be developed. in the digital environment to connect intent, behavior, and retention. No prior research has attempted to integrate these concepts into a single cohesive model (Cheung et al. 2003). To do this, they presented the MIAC model, a combination of two previous models. The attitude theoretical model provides a description of the underlying framework that we begin with (ATM). only the most important aspects of consumer decision-making at the intention and adoption stages are taken into consideration here. Second, there is something that has been dubbed the "expectation-confirmation model" (ECM for short) (Lilien et al. 1992). This concept sought to explain how buyers behave after they've made a purchase (Oliver's 1980). It states that customers compare the product's actual performance to their expectations. Consumers are happy if the first performance is greater than or equal to the second. Contented clients are more likely to make use of the data system

(Bhattacherejee 2001). As a result, contentment serves as a moderator between the adoption and continuation piece.

Figure 2 Intention, Adoption and Continuance (MIAC) Model (Cheung et al. (2003), p. 199)

4.1 Intention

Online shopping intent can be deduced with the use of technology acceptance theories. Researchers have been interested in what drives people to interact with and adopt new forms of technology since the 1970s. Multiple notions and theories have emerged because of this. These ideas are applicable to explaining why customers choose to make purchases from an online retailer. This is mostly because virtual stores are only user-friendly informational tools. A dedicated portion of this literature study will provide in-depth explanations of each of these models (Cheung et al. 2003). The deliberate behavior of consumers can be influenced by several different circumstances. The vast majority of research are in agreement that trust and perceived risk are crucial elements at this phase of the customer journey for online buyers. As an adjunct, we discovered that the nature of the product itself and its cost had significant impacts. Books and music CDs, for instance, are common examples of items that consumers buy online because they don't need to be physically examined before purchase. The reputation and quality of an online retailer's service are also crucial (Ruyter et al 2001). Customers who are shopping for a product online often stick to reputable vendors, so they don't have to deal with potential issues like being scammed.

4.2 Adoption

Many different types of factors affect the rate of consumer behavior adoption. Several empirical research have attempted to quantify the effect of various factors on the adoption phase of online purchasing behavior (Cheung et al. 2003). In terms of demographics, studies have mostly focused on the influence of income, gender, age, and education on users' adoption of online purchasing behavior (Bhatnagar et al. 2000). Privacy, security, and reputation are some of the merchant traits that have been shown to influence consumers' willingness to engage in e-commerce (Lee (2002), Ward et al. (2000))

4.3 Continuance

Consumer behavior research following an online purchase is a relatively new area of study. According to Cheung et al. (2003), preliminary study on what motivates online shoppers to make recurring purchases began in the late 1990s. Bhattacharjee's (2001) study, for example, provides a paradigm for comprehending this stage. His framework is based on the psychological notion of confirmation bias (ECT). He discovered that after feeling high degrees of loyalty, contentment, and confirmation, buyers are substantially more inclined to make repeat online transactions. Other studies have been undertaken to determine the effects of various variables on this stage of online shoppers' journeys.

4. Culture

The cultural values model developed by Hofstede (2011) is now the most popular framework for evaluating the impact of cultural variations on marketing and management research. This model was initially built based on employees of IBM, and it has since been proven to accurately describe wide-ranging cultural differences at the national level (Smith et al., 2013). Hofstede (1991) identified four universal cultural characteristics: power distance, individualism, masculinity, and uncertainty avoidance and long-term orientation.

An individual's position in society and their connection to others in positions of authority are examples of power distance. Low power distance nations are largely consisted of Western countries, such as in the situations of the US, Australia, and Israel, whereas high power distance nations include India, China, and other countries like Mexico (Rinne et al., 2012).

- The term "individualism collectivism" describes the dynamic between an individual and a community. In this respect, collective adherence to the norm and group decisions are more significant than individuals' needs or wants in Asian cultures (Fam Waller 2003).
- Masculinity focuses on the biological aspects of being born a male, whereas femininity considers the social consequences. either a male or a female Most East Asian countries, with the exception of Japan, score worse than most Western nations when it comes to masculinity (Hofstede et al., 1998).

When we talk about "uncertainty avoidance," we're referring to strategies for controlling your anger and other strong feelings in times of unpredictability. In the meanwhile, East Asian countries One of the most significant cultural distinctions between East Asians has been discovered as a preference for certainty over ambiguity, even though both groups tend to score similarly on other measures. For instance, Asian countries like Japan and Taiwan do highly on a measure of their propensity to shun risk. While both China and Singapore have high scores on the trait of uncertainty avoidance, the former country has a far lower score than the latter (Hofstede et al., 2010).

An individual's level of concentration is a key indicator of their long-term direction. Efforts that look to the future rather than the past or the present (Minkov Hofstede, 2011). The top four nations in this category are all located in East Asia. It includes countries including South Korea, Taiwan, Japan, and China (Hofstede Minkov, 2010).

In addition, there has been a new push in the literature to extend the number of factors considered by centering on cultural differences (Minkov Hofstede,2011). The investigation of this topic also includes a further dimension. things that are emblematic of a nation's culture

The indulgence-restraint spectrum describes the range of individual happiness that people in each culture are encouraged to pursue on their own. National cultures tend to indulge less than Western ones and Oceania. Asians, Africans, and South Americans tend to be more reserved. Nevertheless, such a dimension was rarely employed in the prevailing literature. and most related research has only begun (Sun et al., 2019).

For the most part, research on online shopping habits has focused on U.S. populations (Cayla Arnould, 2008). A small number of research have attempted to generalize across cultures; for instance, Ko et al. (2004) analyzed perceived risk differences between Koreans and Americans, suggesting that Korean users, who are members of a collectivist culture, display a greater degree of

social risk. In a study of international consumers, Capece et al. (2013) surveyed participants in both Italy and China. The cultural values of power distance and individualism in Italy and of long-term orientation and uncertainty avoidance in China explain why the former are more likely to trust and adopt e-commerce than the latter. Consumers in Spain and Columbia were studied by Pea-Garca et al. (2020), who found that in markets with a short-term orientation, like Colombia, buying impulse is a predictor of online purchase intention and that appropriate design strategies for online stores that can trigger purchases should be developed. Despite this expanding body of literature, to the best of our knowledge, little study has addressed the combined influence of cultural variables on intention to use an online e-commerce platform, privacy concerns, and trust. This is unexpected given the powerful effect culture has on consumer habits. In fact, research by De Mooij and Hofstede suggests that exposure to other cultures may lead to noticeable variations in how people think, as well as how they approach and utilize new forms of knowledge and technology (2011). In a similar vein, they may cause shifts in the intensity of feelings and underlying motivations among consumers (Zollo et al., 2018).

5.1 Comparison of Hofstede Cultural dimension of Morocco and United Kingdom

Figure 3 Cultural dimension of Morocco and United Kingdom (Hofstede Insights, 2022)

5.2 Power Distance

Morocco has a hierarchical social structure, scoring 70 percent. As a result, people have come to

accept a hierarchical system in which everyone has a position and does not require more justification. Power distance society, which believes in minimizing inequities between people, ranks Britain at 35. It's interesting to note that the percentage of Britons with Parkinson's Disease (PD) is lower among the wealthy than among the working class. First, the PDI scores appear out of sync with Britain's historically established class system. They show that there is tension in British society between the importance of social status at birth and the belief, shared by many, that one's birthplace should not be a barrier to achievement.

5.3 Individualism

A collectivist society index of 46 is assigned to Morocco. Members of the 'group,' whether they be family or friends, can sustain their connection throughout time. In a collectivist society, devotion to the community is prioritized over adherence to the law and other social norms. With a score of 89, the United Kingdom is among the top Individualist nations. The British are widely regarded to be exceedingly introverted and secretive. Determine early on what you want to get out of life and what you can bring to the world in your own special way.

5.4 Masculinity

Morocco's score on this dimension is 53, which is inconclusive. When a person's Feminine score is low, society places a premium on care for others and quality of life. In a Feminine society, quality of life is the measure of success, not standing out from the crowd. Society dominated by men: At age 66, Britain is extraordinarily successful and ambitious. The seeming mismatch between the British culture of modesty and understatement and its success-driven value structure is a significant source of bewilderment for foreigners. To comprehend them, the ability to "read between the lines," as the British say, is crucial. The full meaning is not always conveyed by the spoken words. Compared to the Scandinavian countries, people in the United Kingdom have a well-defined employment objective.

5.5 Uncertainty Avoidance

On this dimension, Morocco scores 68, suggesting a significant tendency for avoiding uncertainty. Countries with a high Uncertainty Avoidance adhere to strict standards of belief and conduct and are intolerant of nonconformist behavior and ideas. With a score of 35 on the Uncertainty Avoidance scale, the United Kingdom is content to wake up without knowing what the day will bring and to change their plans when new information becomes available.

5. The UTAUT model

This unified theory is predicated upon several of the theories that have been shown to have the most significant impact on the study of how people accept new technologies. Numerous competing models have been developed to explain human behavior in relation to the introduction of new technologies (Venkatesh et al,2003). These models are each affected by their own unique combination of contributing elements. As a result of this, Venkatesh and several other scientists have investigated each of these ideas and created a unified model that takes into account all of the factors that contribute to acceptance.

Users' willingness to adopt new technology is influenced by three primary factors: User acceptance of new technology is affected by elements such as performance expectations, social influences, effort expectations, and enabling conditions, as stated by Venkatesh et al. (2003). An introduction to "performance expectancy": this term refers to how much an individual anticipates their employment of a certain system to aid them in improving their work output (p.447). Perceived utility, extrinsic motivation and outcome expectations all play a role in this issue. "The degree of easiness connected with the use of the system" is Effort Expectancy (p.450). It's also known as "how much an individual believes that pivotal others think he or her should use the new method" (p.451). It was found by UTAUT that people's propensity to accept cutting-edge electronics is affected by a variety of extraneous variables. One more factor has been established by Venkatesh and co-authors (2003) that not only affects behavioral intention but also results in the adoption of the new technology. Enabling conditions refer to "how confident a user is that the necessary institutional and technical support is in place to make effective use of the system" (p.453). An individual's declared or observed behavioral purpose or actual use is crucial to the efficacy of UTAUT. Things like gender, age, experience, and willingness to use play a role in the process. There are anywhere from two to four mediators in total.

Figure 4: UTAUT (Venkatesh, 2003)

6.1 The study's findings of the technology acceptance

This section summarizes the articles that use the UTAUT model for their research and presents them in table 1.

<u>Study and findings</u>
<u>Abu-Shanab and Pearson (2009):</u> An important aspect of this research is the creation of a thoroughly tested Arabic instrument for use in the assessment of people's attitudes toward new technologies. This is because the results show that the translation process can affect the instrument employed.
<u>Curtis et al. (2010):</u> As the result shows, women tend to see the benefits of social media, while men are more likely to make use of these platforms. Since there is a positive correlation between the UTAUT dimensions and credibility, this may indicate that businesses with more capable public relations departments are more inclined to use social media for business objectives.

<p><u>Zhou et al. (2010):</u></p> <p>The results show that there is a strong correlation between user adoption and Performance Expectation, Task Technology Fit, Social Influence, and Facilitating Conditions. The research also showed a strong connection between Task Technology Fit and Anticipated Performance.</p>
<p><u>Laumer et al. (2010):</u></p> <p>Intent to use an online recruitment system can be predicted by performance expectation, enabling conditions, and subjective norms. These results highlight the potential utility of further study into the moderating effect of Subjective Norm on adoption, particularly in the context of distinct peer groups.</p>
<p><u>Pena-Garcia et al. (2020):</u></p> <p>The results show that there is a significant discrepancy between customers' intentions and their actions, proving that intentions alone are not sufficient predictors of customers' actual behavior.</p>
<p><u>Law et al. (2016):</u></p> <p>found that both the association between perceived ease of use and purchase intent and the relationship between innovativeness and buy intent are partially mediated by attitude and regular online usage. Conclusions Middle-aged consumers are more likely to make purchases online when websites are more inventive and easy to navigate. It's possible (but not guaranteed) that this process will involve some sort of online demeanor or perspective.</p>

Table 1: Summary of articles based on UTAUT model

6. International e-commerce: developed and developing countries

Customers' attitudes regarding internet buying may not reflect the same maturity in established and emerging countries, and as a result, the factors used may fall into a few distinct categories in each of these situations. As a result, we can gain a better knowledge of the background of developing countries by studying both worlds in the e-commerce sector. As a result of this advancement, a new generation of entrepreneurs in developing countries may be more tempted to launch their own ventures. More entrepreneurs will focus on building digital business startups if the factors influencing people's desire to buy online are better understood, benefiting nations' economies. Despite differences in context, review studies on e-commerce adoption (Chang et al. 2005; Abed et al. 2015; Friedrich, 2015; Alfahl et al. 2012) have been limited to providing a generic understanding of this phenomenon without distinguishing between developed and developing economies, and they do not provide a classification scheme for these similar factors.

7. The online buying behavior in Morocco

One of the fastest growing and most exciting markets in Africa is Morocco's online retail sector. According to the UNCTAD's B2C business-to-consumer e-commerce index, Morocco is placed 6th in Africa behind Mauritius, South Africa, Tunisia, Nigeria, and Kenya, and 85th in the world (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development).

The latest report from the Center Monétique Interbancaire CMI indicates that there were a total of 6 million online payment transactions made by bank card on merchant sites affiliated with the CMI in the first half of 2020 (the total amount is 2.9 billion DH during the first half of 2020), with 260,000 of these transactions being made with foreign cards, equaling 180 million DH during the same period.

“The growth of credit card payments is around 21% from one year to the next. This trend will continue for several more years, the potential for inactive payment cards still being very high [Editor’s note Cards used only for ATM withdrawals]. Regarding digital payments made through bank devices (sms banking application, bank website, bank branches), concentrated on the payment of invoices, various taxes and levies, port charges for importers-exporters... growth is 90% per year,” explains Mikael Naciri, Managing Director of the Center Monétique Interbancaire(CMI).

With the advent of the Internet, commerce in Morocco has taken on a more digital 2.0, unstructured aspect. Because most transactions occur outside of the banking circuit and many online merchants accept cash as payment, the quantities generated by these transactions are substantial.

Still, the CMI reports that overall, 67% of e-consumers do their bill paying online. While 37% of online shoppers are interested in apparel and accessories, 27% take care of their utility, transportation, and lodging bills over the internet. Next, 24% of online shoppers use a food delivery service (like Glovo, Jumia, etc.) to get their meals. Finally, 23% of people are paying for online video services (Netflix, Spotify, Youtube, etc.).

“All the indicators (internet, mobile, online sales, etc.) point to the accelerated development of e-commerce in Morocco with major platforms and an increasingly

wide line-up of products and services. If we consider that Moroccans are more and more connected and that mobile uses are spreading more and more every day, e-commerce has very

good days ahead of it", reports Karim Debbar, Managing Director by Glovo Morocco.

However, there is still a significant minority of people who don't shop online because of concerns including poor payment options (17%), products that don't meet their demands (18%), excessively high pricing (10%), shipping problems (9%), and a general lack of trust (7%) among online retailers.

Because of the restrictions imposed on the country, 22% of Moroccans made their first online purchase during this time, becoming first-time e-shoppers who relied on digital channels to acquire non-essential goods.

8. The online buying behavior in United Kingdom

The United Kingdom (UK) has the most developed e-commerce market in all of Europe. The UK's Office of National Statistics predicts that e-commerce sales in the country will reach 693 billion GBP in 2019, a significant rise over 2018. By industry, this year saw the greatest increase in online sales in wholesale and manufacturing. The retail industry in the UK is the most successful in Europe and accounts for about 8% of total e-commerce sales. The coronavirus pandemic may have a major impact on future internet sales figures, as they accounted for roughly 20% of all transactions in 2019. Online retail sales climbed at a faster-than-average rate of 46.1% in 2020, the first year in which this has happened in at least a decade. Recent government estimates indicate that more than 25% of textile and apparel retail sales were generated over the Internet.

More and more people in the United Kingdom prefer to purchase for goods and services online. The preceding year may have seen the highest penetration of internet shopping in the United Kingdom (up to 87%) in 11 years. The most bought items were apparel and sporting goods.

8.1 Affiliations with retailers

There is a wide range of reasons why people shop online, according to more in- depth studies of consumer behavior. Prices and options were identified to be the most important variables in a 2020 survey. While surveys show that debit and credit cards are still the most popular ways to pay, other methods like PayPal and digital wallets from tech giants like Google, Apple, and Amazon are gaining ground. More than a third of UK consumers favor making delayed payments while shopping online. Buy Now Pay Later was most popular for purchases of casual clothing and cosmetics.

9. Research Methodology

This chapter describes the current study's research methods in detail. It begins by describing the sample population. The questionnaire design and format are then described. It also specifies how the surveys will be distributed.

10.1 Study overview

The current investigation was conducted quantitatively and was finished in three stages. This study's first phase was devoted to designing the survey. At this stage, I determined how many respondents the survey needed to generate reliable results. The second phase of this investigation centered on the distribution and gathering of data. The final phase centered on the evaluation and interpretation of the data.

10.2 Research Framework

The UTAUT methodology is employed in this survey. Long before Venkatesh et al made UTAUT, many scientists came up with similar models, like TAM and TPB. It was picked for the first time because it is a brief explanation of eight earlier models that were similar. Also, this method has been a preferred way to start doing business on the Internet. This is due to the fact that it has been utilized in a number of studies that aimed to determine what characteristics affect online purchasing across countries.

10.3 Environments in which surveys are conducted

Two institutions in the United Kingdom and one in Morocco were used to collect the survey data. Survey respondents in the United Kingdom are students at Sunderland University, located in northern England. This institution was founded in 1991 and today has more than 24,796 students enrolled in its programs. An estimated 38% of the global student population are non-natives, with the majority hailing from the United Kingdom. Members of Al Alkhawayn University in Morocco participated in the study. In Morocco, it is the first American-style institution to use English as a medium for instruction. There are now about 2000 students enrolled across the university's three faculties. In addition to its hefty tuition, the university has a rigorous selection process. As a result, many Moroccans do not have access to it.

10.4 Method of sampling

Using a snowball sample strategy, the current survey is sampling. Qualtrics was used to create the survey. Facebook has been my primary method of disseminating the survey to people I know from both the UK and Morocco's universities. Please forward this email to your friends and acquaintances who meet the qualifications, as well. In addition to my personal network, I've looked for Facebook groups associated with these two institutions. I was able to track down a good number, and I've made the survey available in each of them. Three weeks into the survey, the response rate had dropped to 0 for the previous four days, so I decided to stop.

10.5 Research methodologies

The UTAUT methodology is used in the survey. This model shift has also been widely adopted by online retailers. This is largely because it has been used in numerous international studies comparing aspects of online buying.

10.6 The design of the survey

The survey was developed using the UTAUT framework. There have been a lot of studies done to find the best online shopping theories in the literature review. We had to narrow the options down to a more manageable quantity to create a survey that accurately reflected the most relevant models. The initial UTAUT model proposed by Venkatesh et al. (2003a) consisted of four moderators that assessed the strength of the connection between the behavioral intention component and the other variables. To keep things straightforward, this study only examined the effects of a single moderator (gender). This led to the removal of three moderators. The survey questions were designed to elicit thoughtful responses that cut right to the chase. For a representative sample to provide useful feedback, the questions must be easy to understand. A well-designed questionnaire is an essential part of any quantitative investigation (Hays 2008). Each sentence has been polished to precision so that it is clear and concise.

10.7 Questionnaire units

The questionnaire has 23 questions distributed out through three main units. The first unit contains 4 questions intended to elicit information about age, gender, status, and a question about their location either in Morocco or UK. The second unit consists of two questions designed to

assess the frequency of purchase, which is the model's practical application. Respondents must indicate the frequency of their purchases by picking one of five options for each question. The final unit consists of 16 questions designed to assess the various UTAUT model constructs. Respondents must select one response from the five options that comprise the Likert scale (Likert 1932).

10.8 Questions of the survey

Most of the questions in the surveys are based on research. It was not necessary to conduct a prior study for the first three questions that were used to measure country of residence, gender, and status. The UTAUT model's independent construct is built entirely on Venkatesh et al.'s (2003).

10.9 Development of Hypotheses

Four primary questions that this research is aimed at addressing were stated in the study's introduction section. The answers to these questions have been converted into hypotheses.

- **H1:** Performance expectation and behavioral intention are linked in different ways depending on the culture
- **H2:** Differences in culture affect the relationship between effort expectations and behavior plans.
- **H3:** The relationship between social influence and behavior intention is affected by culture.
- **H4:** The relationship between conditions that make shopping easier and actual shopping is affected by culture.

10. Data Analysis

On the information acquired through the survey, confirmatory factor analysis is performed in this chapter. It is broken into two sections: the first outlines the various processes of the Moroccan and the United Kingdom sample's confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The final section compares the results of each country's responses to the various questions.

11. Morocco

In this part we look at the respondent's demographics. Also included are details of the methodology used in the confirmatory factor analysis performed on the statistics from the Moroccan population.

12.1 Demographics

12.2 Gender

The percentage of the female respondents is a little slightly higher than the average for the male. Table shows that 52.53% of the respondents are men while 45.45% are females.

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Male	42.1%	24
2	Female	54.4%	31
3	Non-binary / third gender	3.5%	2
4	Prefer not to say	0%	0
	Total	100%	100

Table 2 : This table presents the gender characteristics of the Moroccan participant sample

12.3 Age

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Between 18-25	68.1%	47
2	Between 25-35	23.2%	16
3	Between 35-45	7.2%	5
4	Between 45-55	1.4%	1
	Total	100%	

Table 3 : The table presents the age characteristic of the Moroccan participant sample

The table 3 above represents the different age groups of the respondents, we note that the dominant age group is between 18-25 years old, 54.55%, this group generally corresponds to young students or even graduates, who are already digitized and active in terms of using the internet, which is taking up more and more space in their daily lives.

Followed by those aged between 25-35 and over 45 who amount to 32.32 % and 11.11% respectively, while the combined proportions of individuals between 35-45 is 2.02%.

12.4 Descriptive analyses

Table 4 shows the statistics that describe the sample from Morocco. The table is set up to show the different types of tools based on their factors. The average of the different tools is between 3.60 and 4.44, and the standard deviation is between 0.88 and 1.69.

Factor	Mean	Standard deviation
Frequency	-	-
Fr1 : How often do you make internet purchases each month?	4.28	1.69
Fr2 : How regularly do you buy something from an online shop?	2.46	1.19
Effort Expectancy	-	-
E1 : My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	3.54	0.99
E2 : It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	3.68	1.15
E3 : The online stores would be simple for me to use?	3.84	0.93
E4 : I can easily learn how to shop at online stores.	3.84	0.97
Social Influence	-	-
S1 : My friends keep telling me that I should buy things online.	3.44	0.99
S2 : People who are significant to me suggest that I should shop online.	3.52	1.05
S3 : People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	3.50	0.99
Performance Expectancy	-	-

P1: Online shopping would be useful in my life?	3.98	1.15
P2: Does online buying help me to save time?	3.68	1.00
P3: Will I have a better chance of buying quality items if I shop online?	3.28	1.08
Intention	-	-
I1: I anticipate to do more of my future shopping online?	4.00	0.88
I2: I anticipate doing future shopping online?	4.16	0.97
I3: I anticipate future online shopping?	4.22	0.93

Table 4 : The descriptive analyses of the Moroccan sample

12.5 Convergent validity average

Convergent validity is used to investigate how various instruments measuring the same variable compare to one another. According to Gefen et al. (2005), convergent validity is met when answers to these measures are similar. In this situation, the values of two crucial parameters determine the validity of a confirmatory factor analysis: In other words, AVE (average variance extracted) and CR (confidence ratio) (Composite reliability) Good convergent validity, necessitates an AVE over 0.5 and a CR above 0.7. (Hair et al.2006)

As can be seen in Table 5, the average retrieved variances for all five components is greater than 0.5. All of the constructs had a composite reliability score of more than 0.7.

	Composite Reliability	AVE
Behavioral Intention	0.96	0.91
Effort Expectancy	0.90	0.70
Facilitating Condition	0.81	0.60
Performance Expectancy	0.86	0.67
Social Influence	0.91	0.78
Use Behavior	0.85	0.75

Table 5 : Convergent validity average of Morocco sample

12.6 Discriminant validity

Discriminant validity findings for the Moroccan samples are displayed in table 7, and they point to a substantial correlation between the various measures and their theoretical construct, rather than a correlation between the measures themselves. Hair et al. (2006) checks the data's discriminant validity by looking at the correlation between the different constructs and the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). In this case, the retrieved average variance (AVE) exceeds the correlation between the various components. All other inter-construct correlations in the table are smaller than the AVEs (bold values in the diagonal). Consequently, the validity of the sample's ability to discriminate among Moroccans is investigated.

	Behavioral Intention	Effort Expectancy	Facilitating Conditions	Performance Expectancy	Social Influence	Use Behavior
Behavioral Intention	0.955					
Effort Expectancy	0.641	0.839				
Facilitating Conditions	0.589	0.426	0.775			
Performance Expectancy	0.442	0.577	0.322	0.823		
Social Influence	0.448	0.429	0.575	0.442	0.886	
Use Behavior	-0.284	-0.536	-0.536	-0.384	-0.500	0.868

Table 6 : The discriminatory validity of the population of Morocco

12.7 Multiple Regression Analyses

Table 8 shows that the theoretical correlations between the UTAUT model's elements are substantial in the Moroccan model. Furthermore, in the Moroccan sample, the correlation between Effort

Expectation and Behavioral Intention is the greatest Beta = 0.527. Furthermore, there is a low correlation among Facilitating Conditions and use behavior Beta = -0.572. The results of these values will be discussed in depth in the next section.

	Beta	P-value
Behavioral Intention ->Use Behavior	0.06	0.636
Effort Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.527	0.000
Facilitating Conditions -> Use Behavior	-0.572	0.000
Performance Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.050	0.688
Social Influence -> Behavioral Intention	0.199	0.109

Table 7 : The multi regression of the Moroccan sample

12.8 R square

The Moroccan sample does not fit the model very well. According to Table 9 , the behavioral intention R square value is 0.44, which is only fair. This indicates that the factors "Effort Expectancy," "Performance Expectancy," and "Social Influence" may each predict 44% of behavioral intention. However, the Use Behavior variable's r square value is only 0.28. Therefore, the method does not provide a good match for the data from Morocco. A possible reason is that the connection between behavioral intention and use behavior is incorrect. This is mostly due to the fact that Actual Use is focused on the here-and-now, whereas Intention looks farther down the road. Because of this, it's possible that the low R square value of this research can be understood.

Dependent value	R square
Behavioral Intention	0.44
Use Behavior	0.28

Table 8 : The R square of the Moroccan sample

13. United Kingdom

13.1 Demographics:

13.2 Gender

The percentage of male respondents is quite greater than the average percentage of male respondents. Table 10 indicates that 52.3% of participants are men and 47.7% are female.

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Male	52.3%	23
2	Female	47.7%	21
3	Non-binary / third gender	0.0%	0
4	Prefer not to say	0.0%	0
	Total	100%	100

Table 9 : This table presents the gender characteristics of the United Kingdom participant's sample

13.4 Age

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Between 18-25	42.6%	20
2	Between 25-35	42.6%	20
3	Between 35-45	12.8%	6
4	Between 45-55	2.1%	1
	Total	100%	100

Table 10 : This table presents the age characteristics of the United Kingdom participant's sample

The table 11 above represents the different age groups of the respondents, we note that there are 2 dominant age group is between 18-25 years old, 42.6 % and between 25-35 years old 42.6% , this group generally corresponds to young students or even graduates, who are already digitized and active in terms of using the internet, which is taking up more and more space in their daily lives.

Followed by those aged between 35-45 and over 45 who amount to % and 12.8% respectively, while the combined proportions of individuals between 35-45 is 2.1%.

13.5 Descriptive Statistics:

Table 12 shows the statistics that describe the United Kingdom sample. The table is set up to show the different types of instruments based on their factors. The average of the different instruments ranges from 2.78 to 4.42, and the standard deviation goes from 0.74 to 1.15.

Factor	Mean	Standard deviation
Frequency	-	-
Fr1 : How often do you make internet purchases each month?	4.26	1.60
Fr2 : How regularly do you buy something from an online shop?	2.78	1.15
Effort Expectancy	-	-
E1 : My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	3.76	1.04
E2 : It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	3.88	1.11
E3 : The online stores would be simple for me to use?	4.02	0.87
E4 : I can easily learn how to shop at online stores.	4.12	0.94
Social Influence	-	-
S1 : My friends keep telling me that I should buy things online.	3.96	0.83
S2 : People who are significant to me suggest that I should shop online.	4.10	0.88
S3 : People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	4.06	0.74
Performance Expectancy	-	-
P1 : Online shopping would be useful in my life?	3.98	1.22
P2 : Does online buying help me to save time?	3.78	1.13

P3: Will I have a better chance of buying quality items if I shop online?	3.74	1.15
Intention	-	-
I1: I anticipate to do more of my future shopping online?	4.36	0.77
I2: I anticipate doing future shopping online?	4.42	0.75
I3: I anticipate future online shopping?	4.40	0.83

Table 11: The descriptive analyses of the United Kingdom sample

13.6 Convergent validity average

the convergent validity testing revealed some issues with one of the constructs. Before eliminating any measurement, the convergent validity was examined, as shown in table 13. The outcome revealed that the "Use Behavior" AVEs was 0.543. This number is under average. As a result, it is necessary to eliminate some measurements in order to increase the data's overall convergent validity.

	Composite Reliability	AVE
Behavioral Intention	0.925	0.805
Effort Expectancy	0.885	0.658
Facilitating Condition	0.839	0.646
Performance Expectancy	0.956	0.879
Social Influence	0.939	0.837
Use Behavior	0.543(1.00)*	0.503

Table 12 : The Convergent validity average of the United Kingdom

Note: 0.543 represents the recommended threshold *1 which represents the values after removing Fr1

13.7 Discriminant validity

There is a larger relationship between the different measures and their associated theoretical constructs than there is between the individual measures themselves, as seen in table 15 of the discriminant validity findings in the United Kingdom sample. The AVEs, shown by the bold values in the table's diagonal, are greater than the correlations between the different constructs, which are

shown by the smaller values on the left and the bottom of the table. This leads us to investigate the discriminant validity of the Finnish sample.

	Behavioral Intention	Effort Expectancy	Facilitating Conditions	Performance Expectancy	Social Influence	Use Behavior
Behavioral Intention	0.89					
Effort Expectancy	0.659	0.81				
Facilitating Conditions	0.738	0.719	0.80			
Performance Expectancy	0.468	0.745	0.412	0.93		
Social Influence	0.552	0.634	0.721	0.369	0.91	
Use Behavior	-0.232	-0.423	-0.434	-0.597	-0.158	0.70

Table 13 : The discriminant validity of the United Kingdom sample

13.8 Multiple Regression Analyses

Table 16 shows that under the UK model, the predicted correlations between the model's variables are not statistically significant. Also, in the Moroccan sample, the strongest link is between Effort Expectation and Behavioral Intention (Beta = 0.519). Also, there isn't much of a link between Performance Expectation and Behavioral Intention (Beta = -0.002). The repercussions of these results are discussed at length in the next section.

	Beta	P-value
Behavioral Intention ->Use Behavior	0.203	0.312
Effort Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.519	0.003
Facilitating Conditions -> Use Behavior	-0.579	0.008

Performance Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	-0.002	0.990
Social Influence -> Behavioral Intention	0.223	0.131

Table 14 : The multi regression analyses of the United Kingdom sample

The sample from the United Kingdom doesn't fit the model all that well. Table 17 shows that the R square value for behavioral intention is 0.46, which is about right. This means that the variables "Effort Expectancy," "Performance Expectancy," and "Social Influence" might all be able to predict 46% of behavioral intention. But the r square value for the Use Behavior variable is only 0.20. So, the model doesn't fit the United Kingdom sample well enough. Possible justifications include the fact that there ought to be a distinct connection between the ideas of Behavioral Intention and Use Behavior. The main reason for this is that Intention is more focused on the future than Actual Use. Because of this, it's possible that the low R square value of this research can be understood.

Dependent value	R square
Behavioral Intention	0.465
Use Behavior	0.206

Table 15 : The R square of the United Kingdom sample

14. Comparative Analysis of Factors between Morocco and the United Kingdom

Factor	Morocco	United Kingdom
Frequency	-	-
Fr1 : How often do you make internet purchases each month?	4.28	4.26
Fr2 : How regularly do you buy something from an online shop?	2.46	2.78
Effort Expectancy	-	-
E1 : My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	3.54	3.76
E2 : It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	3.68	3.88
E3 : The online stores would be simple for me to use?	3.84	4.02
E4 : I can easily learn how to shop at online stores.	3.84	4.12
Social Influence	-	-

S1: My friends keep telling me that I should buy things online.	3.44	3.96
S2: People who are important to me believe that I should buy online?	3.52	4.10
S3: People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	3.50	4.06
Performance Expectancy	-	-
P1: Online shopping would be useful in my life?	3.98	3.98
P2: Does online buying help me to save time?	3.68	3.78
P3: Will I have a better chance of buying quality items if I shop online?	3.28	3.74
Intention	-	-
I1: I anticipate to do more of my future shopping online?	4.00	4.36
I2: I anticipate doing future shopping online?	4.16	4.42
I3: I anticipate future online shopping?	4.22	4.40

Table 16 : Comparative Analysis of Factors between Morocco and the United Kingdom

Means for the two sample groups (Morocco and the United Kingdom) are compared in table 18. In general, most of the constructs' metrics don't differ all that much. Social Influence is one of the constructs where there was a significant mean difference. There, it appears that more people from the United Kingdom make internet purchases than from Morocco.

15. Results and analysis

The current master's thesis's chapter will address the findings from the one before it. The primary purpose of this section is to use the theories from the section on customer behavior to understand the conclusions of the analytical section better. It mostly consists of two components. Morocco is discussed in the first section, and Finland is discussed in the second.

15.1 Morocco

The outcomes of the study of the Morocco sample are discussed in this chapter's first section.

15.2 Hypothesis testing

Table 19 displays the hypotheses that aim to explain the connection between independent variables and the behavioral intention component, as well as those that seek to address the relationship between the constructs themselves. We will focus on testing the first category of hypotheses in this introduction.

Hypothesis	Findings BETA	Conclusion
H.1 : Performance expectation and behavioral intention are linked in different ways depending on the culture [PE -> BI]	0.050	VALID
H.2 : Differences in culture affect the relationship between effort expectations and behavior plans. [EE-> BI]	0.527	VALID
H.3 :The relationship between social influence and behavior intention is affected by culture. [SI -> BI]	0.199	VALID
H.4 : The relationship between conditions that make shopping easier and actual shopping is affected by culture. [FC ->UB]	-0.572	NOT VALID

Table 17 : Hypothesis Testing of The Moroccan sample

The results of the Moroccan sample do not support UTAUT model . As seen in Table 17, this is predominantly due to the beta value of the various relationships are low. As a result of the negative link between Facilitating condition and use behavior (-0.572), the H4 cannot be supported.

Significantly positive significant correlation between Performance Expectation and Behavioral Intention. In this instance, performance expectation relates to the potential advantages of online shopping. Morocco is a nation of shops and square markets where shoppers usually engage in discussion with merchants prior to making purchases.

Even though this form of shopping looks to be popular with tourists, locals often despise it. This is mostly because those in charge of such stores frequently make their own purchasing decisions on who vendors to engage with. Consumers typically rely on their own discretion rather than consider current events or market trends when making purchases. Moreover, such establishments typically lack posted opening hours. Typically, they open and close at will without notifying consumers. All

of these things appear to be eroding the relationship between Moroccan customers and these sorts of businesses. Consequently, people seek alternatives to enhance their purchasing experience. Online shopping is one alternative that could overcome all these issues. Observing the rapid expansion of supermarkets in Morocco is a supporting reason for my prior claim regarding the explanation of the link between Performance Expectation and Behavioral Intention. In Marrakech, there was essentially one large grocery ten years ago. Any Moroccan heading to Marrakech was required to visit this location. This suggests it is possible to predict the likelihood that Moroccans will purchase online based on the convenience of the process. This could suggest that Moroccans are resistant to adopting online purchasing. In fact, they require some time to comprehend it and have the necessary confidence before attempting it. Behavior intention is significantly correlated with social influence. social influence is the temptation an individual experiences from his friends and family to make purchases online (Venkatesh et.al 2003). Compared to all the other connections in the model, this one has the greatest score. This suggests that friends and family have a significant impact on whether a Moroccan makes a purchase online. Morocco as a collectivist society. It proposes that individuals have considerable influence over one another.

The link between Facilitating Conditions and Use behavior is negative. The Facilitating Conditions refer to the instruments and information's required to operate the procedure (Venkatesh et al.2003). Possessing a credit card or the ability to use computers may be among the prerequisites. This relationship has the lowest beta value of all partnerships. This may suggest that the people of Morocco who were surveyed had basic computer knowledge and access to a bank account. Activists on the internet have attributed the ease of conditions in recent years to the widespread availability of legitimate bank cards. The main reason for this is that there are several constraints on the exporting of foreign money due to the monetary situation in Morocco. Investors in Morocco's Internet have claimed that the country's government is preventing e-commerce from expanding. The government has addressed this problem by requiring banks to issue credit cards good for internet transactions in Morocco and other countries, using a predetermined yearly budget. The banks have been actively promoting these new cards. The results of this research show that customers are now aware that all necessary conditions for making purchases online have been satisfied. The link between supportive environments and behavior modification would certainly be greater if this research had been completed a few years earlier.

15.3 United Kingdom

The first part of this chapter delves into the data gathered from the United Kingdom.

15.4 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Findings BETA	Conclusion
H.1 : Performance expectation and behavioral intention are linked in different ways depending on the culture [PE -> BI]	-0.002	NOT VALID
H.2 : Differences in culture affect the relationship between effort expectations and behavior plans. [EE-> BI]	0.519	VALID
H.3 :The relationship between social influence and behavior intention is affected by culture. [SI -> BI]	0.223	VALID
H.4 : The relationship between conditions that make shopping easier and actual shopping is affected by culture. [FC ->UB]	-0.579	NOT VALID

Table 18 : Hypothesis testing of the United Kingdom sample

The UTAUT model is not supported by the UK sample. Table 20 shows that this is the case since the betas of the various relationships were low. As a consequence of the negative correlations between the Facilitating state and the usage behavior (-0.002 and (-0.579), respectively), H1 and H4 are not supported.

The table displays the various betas for the various correlations between the variables. The study examines each relationship in detail in the section that follows. The Performance Expectancy and Behavioral Intention are negatively correlated. Before deciding to shop online, UK citizens appear to be somewhat interested in the benefits that could result from doing so. This might be explained by the fact that they are already accustomed to online buying. They are aware of what to anticipate from this form of buying as a result. As a result, pushing them to have an aim to carry this kind of purchasing is no longer a significant impact. However, because they are unfamiliar with this method of buying, Moroccans fared better in this connection. As a result, people have higher expectations from this form of buying. The expectation of effort and behavioral intention are positively correlated. When it comes to using online stores, the UK population seems to give a lot of consideration to the effort expected. This indicates that people favor using straightforward, user-friendly web stores. This might be explained by how well-developed online commerce is in the United Kingdom. As a result, there are many online retailers, and UK customers can choose the one that makes shopping the easiest for them. Although there aren't many stores in Morocco, People will put in the effort to figure out how to use the internet to shop if they find an attractive enough deal. The social influence and behavioral intention are positively correlated. The social influence on internet purchases appears to be a big concern for the UK population.

Hofstede et al. (1988) defined the UK as an individualistic nation. This indicates that interpersonal relationships are weaker than they are in nations. The results of the present investigation contradict Hofstede's theory. This is primarily due to the UK population's strong concern for social influence when making internet purchases. Morocco remains a collective country, hence the relationship strength is similar there. People are therefore proud to demonstrate to others their ability to use new technology and make purchases online.

The Facilitating Conditions and Use Behavior have a bad association. The findings demonstrate that UK citizens assume that having a computer and a bank card are prerequisites for conducting online shopping. Nearly equal levels of relationship strength exist between the two nations. This is primarily since both share the same concept of "Facilitating Conditions."

16 Conclusion

In this final section, the master's thesis is summed up. There are three primary sections to this chapter. In the first section, we discuss the study's significance in general. As promised, this chapter's second half is devoted to critiquing the caveats of the current investigation. Finally, this chapter concludes with suggestions for further research.

16.1 Academic Contribution

16.3 Morocco case

The study's findings may be valuable in persuading a broader audience to attempt internet buying. The current findings could be utilized to create promotional content like television ads and magazine features to encourage larger understanding of this innovative technology. There are several ways in which this study can improve online shopping can be improved in Morocco:

1. Increasing the number of online payment options: The study shows that the facilitating conditions need to be improved there are relatively few options for online payments in Morocco, which can act as a barrier to entry for potential customers. Increasing the number and variety of payment options would make it easier for people to purchase goods and services online.
2. Improving logistics and delivery infrastructure: For e-commerce to truly thrive in Morocco, it is essential that there is an efficient logistics and delivery infrastructure in place. This will ensure that goods can be delivered promptly and without any issues.
3. Providing more support for online businesses: There is currently relatively little support available for businesses that operate online in Morocco. This needs to be changed for e-commerce to grow in the country. Providing financial and legal assistance, as well as offering advice on how to set up and run an online business, would be a great help.
4. Encouraging more people to shop online: One of the main challenges facing e-commerce in Morocco is the low level of uptake by consumers. This is often due to a lack of trust in online shopping, as well as a lack of awareness of the benefits. Encouraging more people to shop online through marketing and education campaigns would help to boost the e-commerce sector.

16.4 United Kingdom case

The findings of this study may be implemented by select retailers to boost conversion rates. There is always an opportunity to increase sales at this type of store in the UK. Here is a rundown of the most vital ones that might be implemented to increase traffic to the online store and boost the percentage of customers who make a purchase. The United Kingdom is one of the few places where social influence remains significant. For this reason, there are several ways that social influence can be improved in online shopping in the United Kingdom:

1. Use social media platforms to engage with potential customers and promote special offers.
2. Use customer testimonials and social proof to build trust and confidence.
3. Make it easy for customers to share their positive experiences with their social networks.
4. Use social influencers to reach a wider audience and promote your brand.
5. Encourage customer feedback and use it to improve the customer experience.

16.5 Practical Implications of the Theory

The current study's first major contribution is the identification of cultural influences on consumers' preferences and habits when shopping online. Now more than ever, thanks to advances in communication technology, the world's cultural divides are narrowing. This is largely because most people everywhere consume the similar "culture-shaping content," including films and songs. Comparing two very diverse cultures like Finland and Morocco revealed that cultural norms affect consumers' propensity to shop online. The results also demonstrated, however, that the effect is not particularly noteworthy because of the little variations in the relative importance of the correlations between the various factors. The findings might shed light on how to best design for international markets. Building an effective online store requires attention to detail and an understanding of the buyer personas. To understand what elements influence consumers' propensity to make purchases online, businesses need to invest in skilled marketers and time-consuming market research. As a result, the findings of this research may provide valuable direction for companies of this type seeking to create successful cross-cultural online stores. This is achieved mostly by placing increased emphasis on certain determinants that are immune to cultural shifts.

16.6 Finding Summary

Most of the data from the investigation agreed with the hypothesis. All the Hypothesis made in the table 21 above were correct. Facilitating condition, Performance Expectancy, H.4 for Morocco, and H1 and H2 for the United Kingdom, was the only hypothesis that did not receive sufficient support. The UTAUT model, however, is reinforced by the fact that all other hypotheses are also supported.

Hypothesis	Morocco	United Kingdom
H.1 : Performance expectation and behavioral intention are linked in different ways depending on the culture [PE -> BI]	Valid	Not valid

H.2 : Differences in culture affect the relationship between effort expectations and behavior plans. [EE-> BI]	Valid	Valid
H.3 :The relationship between social influence and behavior intention is affected by culture. [SI -> BI]	Valid	Valid
H.4 : The relationship between conditions that make shopping easier and actual shopping is affected by culture. [FC ->UB]	Not valid	Not valid

Table 19 : Finding summary of Hypothesis testing between Morocco and United Kingdom

16.7 Research limitation

The results of the current study should be interpreted with caution due to the study's limitations. To start, the current study primarily uses data from students in the United Kingdom and Morocco for its primary samples. It could be argued that students at universities are not typical of the population at large. The cultural difference between the two nations is smaller than it otherwise would be because of the youthful population and high levels of education in both countries (Ko et al 2004). It's also worth noting that university students may not provide a reliable representation of the general Moroccan population. This is mostly because most students cannot be considered financially independent. Second, no good or service was the target of this investigation. Perhaps this is where the present investigation falls short. This is because users' interpretations of the questions may vary from what would be expected if the survey were targeted to a certain product or service. Third, this research examines Morocco and the United Kingdom as though they were completely different cultures. The fact is, though, that both nations have a wide range of cultural traditions. So, the distance between people's cultures within a country may be greater than that across countries.

16.8 Further Research

In this study, further investigation is needed primarily in two areas. To begin, the current research does not compare the online shopping behaviors of Moroccans and British regarding a particular product or service. Considering a particular service or product may lead to various outcomes. Second, in both investigations, the online-shopping-related R square was relatively low, suggesting that it would be advisable to examine other variables to identify those that may have influenced the users' actions. Third, if the cultures of these two nations are researched in greater depth, the findings of this research may be more specific. So, we propose doing the study again, this time accounting for the inherent differences between the British and Moroccan ways of life.

17. Personal Development

17.1 KOLB-based reflective model

Reflecting on the process of writing my thesis, Choosing my research topic, developing my methodology, and writing up my findings have all given me a fresh perspective on learning that has inspired me to continue pushing for academic excellence. Everything I've gone through and experienced on this educational journey is unique. My difficulties with academic writing, in the beginning, were ultimately worth it since I learned to see and understand the world in a different way. I will write my personal experience based on the KOLB experimental model.

17.2 Concrete experience

Since deciding on my study topic and completing my proposal, the words "thesis writing" have stuck in my head. Inspirational tales of friends' experiences writing theses and their subsequent achievements have been passed on to me. In equal parts, I was fascinated, encouraged, and frightened by their experiences. My supervisor eventually suggested I switch from my initial, too-broad topic—consumer behavior—to a narrower one so that I could easily secure legal form clearance. To get a good grade and finish the paper on time, I had to work quickly.

For about a month, I moved around between many fields of study before settling on one that truly caught my attention. After much consideration, I decided to study the similarities and differences in online behavior between Morocco and the United Kingdom due to cultural differences. I was surprised to learn, upon moving to the UK, how at ease people are with making internet purchases. Meanwhile, online businesses in Morocco are still having difficulties attracting customers to purchase their products. At first, I assumed that higher levels of income and education would be the primary

factors encouraging Internet use in Britain. The longer we were there, the more I became aware of additional cultural factors that can impact people's choices to shop online in the UK. From talking to my British colleagues, I've learned that the British have a higher rate of trust in internet retailers than the Moroccans do. Instead of continuing to guess, I decided to do a research study to investigate the cultural differences between the United States and the United Kingdom and try to figure out why online shopping is becoming more popular in the UK.

Fearing the worst, I discuss the topic I've chosen with my superior. I had gotten positive feedback about the topics, but she warned me about the complexity of the subject.

17.3 Reflective observation

Another challenging task that must be accomplished during research is data collection. When I was feeling down, I would have mental conversations with myself. Long conversations with myself ensued often; however, I never caught on to what I was saying. One of my classmates called me as I was mulling over how to go about setting up data collection tools, and he voiced certain worries he had. His advice was that we should talk to the head honcho about how information is gathered. I went to see my boss about the problems we were having. She gave a thorough breakdown of the machinery, how to maintain it, and how reliable it is. The discussion defined data collection tools, discussed how to properly prepare for them, and more. Depending on the type of data, I found that different instruments are used (quantitative or qualitative). I was advised that information is crucial to every research project. Because of this, I went ahead and made a tool. When gathering information, I decided to employ a questionnaire. I created the survey using the UTAUT model theory and the Likert scale. Following the completion of the first draft of the questionnaire, it took me a few days to complete the questionnaire. One of the most difficult challenges I had to deal with was the distribution of the questionnaire. I shared my poll primarily through Facebook friends, groups, and forums; it took me a long time to obtain 100 participants. It was hard because the participation rate was often too low. To get more people to take the survey, I had to put in a lot of work and send it to a lot of platforms.

17.4 Abstract conceptualization

For the first week following data collection, I had no clue what to do or how to think about evaluating and understanding the data. As part of my research, I read a few scholarly articles and master's theses that were relevant to my subject. I highlighted every section pertaining to data analysis. Even while I

learned some helpful principles about data analysis and interpretation from these books, they weren't enough to propel me forward. When I went to my boss with a few hypotheses in mind, he suggested I do some sort of descriptive as well as mathematical analysis. Since I wanted to give a thorough, professional examination of the topic, I focused on studies that had gone to great lengths to draw its conclusions. I spent days researching the topic before figuring out how to put together my thesis. The UTAUT model theory appealed to me because of its flexibility in terms of the variables it employs, such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and use behavior; however, I was particularly interested in the latter because my paper examines the influence of culture on internet usage in Morocco and the United Kingdom. My study requires me to evaluate the data I got from a survey, so I've been spending a lot of time learning how to utilize SPSS and, more specifically, Smart PLS. According to her, this is the most crucial part of the research process since it is at this stage that the researcher critically evaluates the data, makes sense of the facts in light of the available literature, and analyses the significance of the data through a theoretical lens. At last, she was able to draw some broad conclusions. In the course of the next several days, I was able to formulate hypotheses about how to analyze and interpret the data. Then, after much effort, I managed to insert the necessary data and my interpretation into the first draft. It lacked polish and felt incomplete. I changed the first two to conform to standard writing style.

17.5 Active experimentation:

In conclusion, conducting research in such a way that it is both fruitful and used as a model is extremely difficult. The fundamentals of research, such as how to frame effective questions and work through issues that initially appear to have no clear answers, were drilled into me. Later, I was able to use this experience to put forth research proposals with greater assurance and expand my understanding of the research process. Students' exposure to research might take numerous forms. At this point, it's most critical to zero in on the researcher's own preferences, both in terms of what he or she enjoys doing and what he or she dislikes doing (which might be just as important). Even though our research won't provide results quickly, we shouldn't let that dampen our spirits. Dedication, hard work, and adherence to the protocol are all prerequisites for successful study. I got out of bed and got to work on making my goal a reality. There are times when my experience of writing a master's thesis as a research newbie provides me with a highly inspiring story worth investigating further. In the end, I owe great gratitude to the holy people whose help and encouragement made writing my thesis such

a delight. I especially want to thank my respected mentors and the supervisor, who helped me a lot as I worked on this paper by giving me feedback, support, and encouragement.

17. Appendix

Figure 5 : Consumer Decision Making Process

Figure 2. Intention, Adoption and Continuance (MIAC) Model (Cheung et al. (2003), p. 199)

Figure 3: Cultural dimension of Morocco and United Kingdom (Hofstede Insights, 2022)

Study and findings
Abu-Shanab and Pearson (2009): Findings indicate that the translation process can impact the instrument used - better testing of backward translation methods will produce better results – an important contribution of this study is the development of a well-tested Arabic instrument in the field of technology acceptance.
Curtis et al. (2010): The finding reveals that females view social media as advantageous, whereas males are more confident in actively using social media. Firms with competent public relations teams are more likely to adopt social media for business purposes - the positive association between UTAUT dimensions and credibility suggests the possibility of a larger adoption of social media.
Zhou et al. (2010): the findings reveal that Performance Expectation, Task Technology Fit, Social Influence, and Facilitating Conditions have substantial effects on user adoption. The study also highlighted the substantial relationship between Task Technology Fit and Expected Performance.
Laumer et al. (2010): Performance Expectancy, Facilitating Conditions, and Subjective Norms are all relevant predictors of intent to use an e-recruitment system. The findings suggest that controlling adoption research for diverse peer groups and the differentiating influence of Subjective Norm on adoption may be valuable.
Pena-Garcia et al. (2020): The results demonstrate a clear gap between intention and actual behavior, confirming that such an intention is an insufficient predictor of the customer's real behavior.
Law et al. (2016): found that both attitude and regular online usage somewhat mediate the relationship between innovativeness and buy intent, as well as the relationship between perceived ease of use and purchase intent. The findings indicate that when middle-aged consumers are more innovative and have an easier time navigating website, they are more inclined to make online purchases. This procedure may or may not entail online behavior or attitude.

Table 1: Summary of articles based on UTAUT model

Morocco Findings

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Male	42.1%	24
2	Female	54.4%	31
3	Non-binary / third gender	3.5%	2
4	Prefer not to say	0%	0
	Total	100%	100

Figure 1: This table presents the gender characteristics of the Moroccan participant sample

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Between 18-25	68.1%	47
2	Between 25-35	23.2%	16
3	Between 35-45	7.2%	5
4	Between 45-55	1.4%	1
	Total	100%	

Figure 2: The table presents the age characteristic of the Moroccan participant sample

Factor	Mean	Standard deviation
Frequency	-	-
Fr1: How many times do you shop online in a month?	4.28	1.69
Fr2: How frequently do you shop online?	2.46	1.19
Effort Expectancy	-	-
E1: My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	3.54	0.99
E2: It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	3.68	1.15
E3: The online stores would be simple for me to use?	3.84	0.93
E4: Learning to shop at online stores is simple for me?	3.84	0.97
Social Influence	-	-
S1: My close friends believe that I should buy online?	3.44	0.99
S2: People who are important to me believe that I should buy online?	3.52	1.05
S3: People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	3.50	0.99
Performance Expectancy	-	-
P1: Online shopping would be useful in my life?	3.98	1.15
P2: Online shopping allows me to save more time?	3.68	1.00
P3: If I shop online, I will have a greater chance of purchasing quality items?	3.28	1.08
Intention	-	-
I1: In the future, I plan to shop online?	4.00	0.88
I2: I anticipate doing future shopping online?	4.16	0.97
I3: I anticipate future online shopping?	4.22	0.93

Table 4: The descriptive analyses of the Moroccan sample

	Composite Reliability	AVE
Behavioral Intention	0.96	0.91
Effort Expectancy	0.90	0.70
Facilitating Condition	0.81	0.60
Performance Expectancy	0.86	0.67
Social Influence	0.91	0.78
Use Behavior	0.85	0.75

Table 5: Convergent validity average of Morocco sample.

Item / Factor	Loadings
Use Behavior (AVE = 0.753, CR =0.859)	
Fr.1 How many times do you shop online in a month?	0.919
Fr.2 How frequently do you shop online?	0.813
Performance Expectancy (AVE =0.677, CR = 0.862)	
P.1 I would find shopping online useful in my life	0.915
P.2 Shopping online enables me to save more time	0.726
P.3 If I use online shops, I will increase my chances of purchasing good products.	0.817
Effort Expectancy (AVE = 0.704, CR = 0.904)	
E.1 My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	0.810
E.2 It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	0.906
E.3 The online stores would be simple for me to use?	0.879
E.4 Learning to shop at online stores is simple for me?	0.752
Social Influence (AVE = 0.785, CR =0.916)	
S.1 My close friends believe that I should buy online?	0.915
S.2 People who are important to me believe that I should buy online?	0.889
S.3 People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	0.852
Facilitating conditions (AVE = 0.601, CR =0.818)	
F.1 Online shopping would be useful in my life?	0.717
F.2 Online shopping allows me to save more time?	0.765
F.3 If I shop online, I will have a greater chance of purchasing quality items?	0.839
Behavioral Intention (AVE =0.911, CR =0.969)	
I.1 In the future, I plan to shop online?	0.937
I.2 I anticipate doing future shopping online?	0.973
I.3 I anticipate future online shopping?	0.953

Table 6: The confirmatory factor analyses of final loadings of the Moroccan sample

	Behavioral Intention	Effort Expectancy	Facilitating Conditions	Performance Expectancy	Social Influence	Use Behavior
Behavioral Intention	0.955					
Effort Expectancy	0.641	0.839				
Facilitating Conditions	0.589	0.426	0.775			
Performance Expectancy	0.442	0.577	0.322	0.823		
Social Influence	0.448	0.429	0.575	0.442	0.886	
Use Behavior	-0.284	-0.536	-0.536	-0.384	-0.500	0.868

Table 7: The discriminant validity of the Moroccan sample

	Beta	P-value
Behavioral Intention -> Use Behavior	0.06	0.636
Effort Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.527	0.000
Facilitating Conditions -> Use Behavior	-0.572	0.000
Performance Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.050	0.688
Social Influence -> Behavioral Intention	0.199	0.109

Table 8: The multi regression of the Moroccan sample

Dependent value	R square
Behavioral Intention	0.44
Use Behavior	0.28

Table 9: The R square of the Moroccan sample

United Kingdom Findings

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Male	52.3%	23
2	Female	47.7%	21
3	Non-binary / third gender	0.0%	0
4	Prefer not to say	0.0%	0
	Total	100%	100

Figure 3: This table presents the gender characteristics of the United Kingdom participant's sample

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Between 18-25	42.6%	20
2	Between 25-35	42.6%	20
3	Between 35-45	12.8%	6
4	Between 45-55	2.1%	1
	Total	100%	100

Figure 4: This table presents the age characteristics of the United Kingdom participant's sample

Factor	Mean	Standard deviation
Frequency	-	-
Fr1: How many times do you shop online in a month?	4.26	1.60
Fr2: How frequently do you shop online?	2.78	1.15
Effort Expectancy	-	-
E1: My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	3.76	1.04
E2: It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	3.88	1.11
E3: The online stores would be simple for me to use?	4.02	0.87
E4: Learning to shop at online stores is simple for me?	4.12	0.94
Social Influence	-	-
S1: My close friends believe that I should buy online?	3.96	0.83
S2: People who are important to me believe that I should buy online?	4.10	0.88
S3: People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	4.06	0.74
Performance Expectancy	-	-
P1: Online shopping would be useful in my life?	3.98	1.22
P2: Online shopping allows me to save more time?	3.78	1.13
P3: If I shop online, I will have a greater chance of purchasing quality items?	3.74	1.15
Intention	-	-
I1: In the future, I plan to shop online?	4.36	0.77
I2: I anticipate doing future shopping online?	4.42	0.75
I3: I anticipate future online shopping?	4.40	0.83

Table 12: The descriptive analyses of the United Kingdom sample

	Composite Reliability	AVE
Behavioral Intention	0.925	0.805
Effort Expectancy	0.885	0.658
Facilitating Condition	0.839	0.646
Performance Expectancy	0.956	0.879
Social Influence	0.939	0.837
Use Behavior	0.543(1.00)*	0.503

Table 13: The Convergent validity average of the United Kingdom

Item / Factor	Loadings
Use Behavior (AVE = 0.504, CR =0.549)	
Fr.1 How many times do you shop online in a month?	0.100
Fr.2 How frequently do you shop online?	0.999
Performance Expectancy (AVE = 0.879, CR = 0.956)	
P.1 I would find shopping online useful in my life	0.953
P.2 Shopping online enables me to save more time	0.945
P.3 If I use online shops, I will increase my chances of purchasing good products.	0.915
Effort Expectancy (AVE = 0.658, CR = 0.885)	
E.1 My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	0.779
E.2 It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	0.825
E.3 The online stores would be simple for me to use?	0.835
E.4 Learning to shop at online stores is simple for me?	0.805
Social Influence (AVE = 0.837, CR =0.939)	
S.1 My close friends believe that I should buy online?	0.936
S.2 People who are important to me believe that I should buy online?	0.884
S.3 People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	0.924
Facilitating conditions (AVE = 0.852, CR =0.920)	
F.1 Online shopping would be useful in my life?	0.938
F.2 Online shopping allows me to save more time?	0.907
Behavioral Intention (AVE = 0.805, CR =0.925)	
I.1 In the future, I plan to shop online?	0.888
I.2 I anticipate doing future shopping online?	0.936
I.3 I anticipate future online shopping?	0.865

Table 14: The confirmatory analyses of the United Kingdom sample

	Behavioral Intention	Effort Expectancy	Facilitating Conditions	Performance Expectancy	Social Influence	Use Behavior
Behavioral Intention	0.89					
Effort Expectancy	0.659	0.81				
Facilitating Conditions	0.738	0.719	0.80			
Performance Expectancy	0.468	0.745	0.412	0.93		
Social Influence	0.552	0.634	0.721	0.369	0.91	
Use Behavior	-0.232	-0.423	-0.434	-0.597	-0.158	0.70

Table 15: The discriminant validity of the United Kingdom sample

	Beta	P-value
Behavioral Intention -> Use Behavior	0.203	0.312
Effort Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.519	0.003
Facilitating Conditions -> Use Behavior	-0.579	0.008
Performance Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	-0.002	0.990
Social Influence -> Behavioral Intention	0.223	0.131

Table 16: The multi regression analyses of the United Kingdom sample

Dependent value	R square
Behavioral Intention	0.465
Use Behavior	0.206

Table 17: The R square of the United Kingdom sample

Factor	Morocco	United Kingdom
Frequency	-	-
Fr1: How many times do you shop online in a month?	4.28	4.26
Fr2: How frequently do you shop online?	2.46	2.78
Effort Expectancy	-	-
E1: My interactions with online retailers would be transparent and understandable?	3.54	3.76
E2: It would be simple for me to learn how to shop from online stores?	3.68	3.88
E3: The online stores would be simple for me to use?	3.84	4.02
E4: Learning to shop at online stores is simple for me?	3.84	4.12
Social Influence	-	-
S1: My close friends believe that I should buy online?	3.44	3.96
S2: People who are important to me believe that I should buy online?	3.52	4.10
S3: People at work have been encouraging me to shop online?	3.50	4.06
Performance Expectancy	-	-
P1: Online shopping would be useful in my life?	3.98	3.98
P2: Online shopping allows me to save more time?	3.68	3.78
P3: If I shop online, I will have a greater chance of purchasing quality items?	3.28	3.74
Intention	-	-
I1: In the future, I plan to shop online?	4.00	4.36
I2: I anticipate doing future shopping online?	4.16	4.42
I3: I anticipate future online shopping?	4.22	4.40

Table 18: The Comparison of Means between both Morocco and United Kingdom

Hypothesis	Findings BETA	Conclusion
H.1 [PE -> BI]	0.050	SUPPORTED
H.2 [EE-> BI]	0.527	SUPPORTED
H.3 [SI -> BI]	0.199	SUPPORTED
H.4 [FC ->UB]	-0.572	NOT SUPPORTED

Table 19 : Hypothesis Testing of The Moroccan sample

Hypothesis	Morocco	United Kingdom
H.1 Performance Expectance ->Behavioral intention	Supported	Not Supported
H.2 Effort Expectancy -> Behavioral intention	Supported	Supported
H.3 Social Influence ->Behavioral Intention	Supported	Supported
H.4 facilitating Condition -> Use Behavior	Not supported	Not supported

Table 20: Hypothesis testing of the United Kingdom sample

Hypothesis	Morocco	United Kingdom
H.1 Performance Expectance ->Behavioral intention	Supported	Not Supported
H.2 Effort Expectancy -> Behavioral intention	Supported	Supported
H.3 Social Influence ->Behavioral Intention	Supported	Supported
H.4 facilitating Condition -> Use Behavior	Not supported	Not supported

Table 21: Finding summary of Hypothesis testing between Morocco and United Kingdom

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